

MODERN INCLUSIVE METHOD FOR FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNERS

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Introduction

The article is devoted to the problem of teaching students with disabilities in English lessons. The urgency of this problem lies in the fact that it is necessary to ensure the general cultural, personal and cognitive development of children with disabilities. The authors proposed methods used for productive teaching for students with disabilities, namely, multimedia and gaming technologies, case technologies, and problem-based learning. In the paper, the authors propose an example of some of the technologies used while working in general education institutions and used when working with children with disabilities in the process of inclusive education. These technologies will help teachers develop the skills and abilities of foreign language communication in children with disabilities.

ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the problem of teaching students, learners, or children with disabilities in English lessons. The relevance of this problem lies in the fact that ensures the general cultural, personal and cognitive development of children.

In the modern world, according to statistical agencies (National Center for Health Statistics; The National Center for Education Statistic; Federal State Statistics Service, etc.), despite the development of various technologies and the field of medical services, doctors observe a significant deterioration in the health of the younger generation, this is especially true for school-age children. In this category of citizens, there are more and more children with the status of "child with disabilities". Researchers of this social group note that such a status seems to be a rather vague concept, since children with minor health problems and disabled children with severe cerebral palsy belong to the same category of students. However, it should be noted that in modern pedagogical science there is a definition of this category of students: students with disabilities are children whose life activity

is accompanied by any restrictions or lack of ability to carry out activities in a way that is considered normal for a person of this age.

After determining the qualitative composition of the studied social group, it is necessary to determine the requirements for the GEF for the studied group of students.

The Federal State Educational Standard of basic general education provides: the variability of the content of educational programs of basic general education (hereinafter referred to as the programs of basic general education), the possibility of creating programs of basic general education of various levels of complexity and focus, taking into account the educational needs and abilities of students, including gifted children, children with disabilities.

For this category of students, inclusive and integrated education is provided. It should be noted that in major cities educational experiments are carried out that allow you to choose different forms of education for the studied category of students.

An analysis of Western and domestic reflection on various aspects of inclusive education indicates the recognition of a clear relationship between the qualitative formation of inclusive educational foundations and the effective and continuous improvement of the bank of methods, forms, teaching tools.

In this case, it is important that the majority of secondary educational institutions (including those in the Astrakhan region) choose inclusive education as the main form of education for children with disabilities, because it opens access to obtaining high-quality, and

most importantly affordable education for this category of citizens.

Inclusive education allows integrating a student with disabilities into the modern educational environment of the institution in such a way that he has the opportunity to receive a quality education on an equal basis with other participants in the educational process.

So, the educational process for students with disabilities should be built taking into account not only their educational needs, but also their educational abilities, which, in our opinion, is a paramount task.

Since foreign language teaching is carried out using a variety of approaches for social groups, among which students with disabilities occupy far from the last positions, in this article we focus on teaching a foreign language to students with disabilities capabilities of the musculoskeletal system. Approbation of the results of the study was carried out on the basis of the Special Correctional Educational Boarding School for Students with Disabilities of the Musculoskeletal System in Astrakhan.

To teach children with disabilities, the teacher needs to have the following information: understand the principles of inclusive education, have an idea about modern health-saving technologies, master the techniques of student-centered presentation of material, as well as productive learning methods.

In modern society, mastering a foreign language is becoming one of the priority tasks, which is largely due to the rapid development of telecommunications networks, various information platforms, as well as distance learning, and their general availability for all categories of the population dictates its own conditions of

existence. Teaching children with disabilities a foreign language is becoming one of the main tasks of the modern educational environment.

In this case, it should be noted that having difficulties in communicating with other children due to the presence of difficulties in movement, this category of children spends a lot of time on the Internet, and to communicate with peers from other countries, you need to know foreign language. In addition, most children with disabilities of the musculoskeletal system undergo rehabilitation abroad (particularly in China), in this case, knowledge of a foreign language would be the solution to the communication problem.

In modern pedagogy, much attention is paid to inclusive education, however, there are practically no methods for teaching a foreign language to this social group, which explains the relevance of the study.

The change of priority from providing a large amount of knowledge to the development of general cultural, personal and cognitive characteristics leads to the fact that it is the practical mastery of a foreign language that comes to the fore.

Note that in the situation under consideration, it comes to the fore listening and speaking, since they form the basis for the formation of skills in two other types of speech activity - reading and writing. That is why in programs for teaching a foreign language to children with disabilities, a special

Emphasis is placed on teaching listening and speaking.

This approach, according to researchers [8], is based on several methodological principles based on the psychophysiological characteristics of the studied group of students.

The principle of mobility.

Children with disabilities tend to be sedentary

way of life, therefore, when teaching a foreign language, it is recommended to adhere to the principle of mobile activities to increase motivation to study the subject, as well as to attract attention, which is often very scattered among representatives of this social group.

The principle of frequent change of activity.

As already noted, children with disabilities often have distracted attention. In order to focus on learning English and performing certain learning activities, they need to change their learning activities frequently.

Creating a language environment and immersion in it. This principle involves the creation of linguocultural conditions for a more complete development of linguistic material.

Frequent listening to language structures. Children with disabilities need to combine listening to the language structure with its repetition, this will overcome the language barrier.

The principle of continuity and repeated repetition of linguistic material. Children with disabilities need to repeat the "introduced" language structures many times in order to ensure long-term storage of these structures in the memory of students. The principle of succession allows you to enter material gradually, following the principle "from simple to complex."

Disclosure of the student's creative abilities through in English. Through a foreign language (due to its diversity), a teacher can not only reveal, but also develop the student's creative abilities, which will positively affect the study of other subjects of the humanities and natural sciences.

At each lesson, which is conducted with a focus on children with disabilities, it is necessary to use various gaming technologies. Tasks presented in the form of a game help children to master the material in a relaxed atmosphere, while each task should have a clearly defined learning goal. Through the use of various didactic games, phonetic, lexical and grammatical skills, which are of paramount practical importance, since teaching children with disabilities a foreign language is carried out primarily based on listening and speaking. Let's consider some types of didactic games successfully

implemented in the course of this study. The authors of these games are the leading methodologists in the field of foreign languages: I. N. Vereshchagina, T. A. Pritykina, O. V. Afanasyeva and others. It should be noted that since the 1960s these games have been used in teaching children a foreign language at an advanced stage of mastering this discipline, however, this game complex is used for the first time when teaching a foreign language to children with disabilities. The description of the games is presented in Table.

Table - Didactic games in English lessons

Game name	Description of game activity
Pen-Friends	Exchange cards with children around the world, communicate with them in a foreign language
Flash	The card with the image is turned back side of the picture. When turning fast picture cards for students they need understand what is depicted and name corresponding lexical unit
Set your imagination free, be slowly	The picture is closed. open picture need to be slow so that students can guess through your imagination top as shown on the card. Word must be named first, who guessed that depicted
Rememberthemissingone	Cards are placed on the board in one straight line. line. After repeated repetition items shown in the picture it is recommended to remove one card from of the presented row, shifting the remaining ones to each other friend. Missing lexical item must be called
Magicraw	This game is similar to Russian gesture game "My triangular cap", only instead of gestures lexical units appear, which need to call each other when the teacher removes cards from the board. For effective application of this game activity it is recommended to use no more than six lexical units, and for their better development the principle of thematic distribution
Readbymylips	The cards are placed randomly on the board. okay. The facilitator says the word using lips and not saying it out loud. Students need match the picture on the board with with the word that the presenter "showed"

Can you understand what I say?

The facilitator describes the word using synonymous lexical units and expressions. The drawn images are located on the board in random order. Need to guess what inquestion

The use of these games in foreign language lessons in teaching students with disabilities showed good results. For this group of students, the practical orientation of knowledge is the main one. Teaching a foreign language is a foreign language communication, communication in a foreign language on a variety of everyday and professional topics. However, it should be noted that communication involves not only oral, but often written communication. The game "Pen Friend" promotes the development of writing skills. The children reacted positively to the game, because behind each postcard there was a real person and real communication with him in a foreign language. This phenomenon has become quite popular in the modern world and is called "postcrossing" - the exchange of postcards with strangers. There is a website www.postcrossing.com on the Internet where children can exchange postcards with people living in different countries.

Multimedia technologies play one of the leading roles in conducting modern classes in the study of a foreign language. For example, you plan to gradually develop students' understanding of English speech. Listening materials can be found on YouTube, TikTok, VKontakte platforms. There are groups on TikTok that post short videos from American and British TV series several times a day with different pronunciations of the same text. Here is practiced understanding English speech with different dialects, voices, speech rates, you can also learn many useful words and expressions.

Job example. Taking a video from YouTube, we will try to understand what it is about, play a "ball game" (the teacher pronounces the phrase in Russian, and the student will have to translate it into English, of course, with using pre-prepared vocabulary, later complete the translation task).

Journey through virtual reality is one of the most effective and intelligible ways to inform students about certain geographical objects, creates the illusion of complete immersion in explored space.

These multimedia technologies are characterized by a high degree of interactivity, allowing you to interact with objects and examine in detail the objects of interest details. Most often, such trips allow you to walk around world capitals, visit famous museums, etc. During a foreign language lesson, such an excursion received a positive response from students. When organizing the education of children with disabilities, it is necessary to think over the use of any gaming technologies.

The game involves all students in the learning process, regardless of their type of temperament. Game activity helps students to go through the processes of self-organization and self-affirmation, motivates them to learn a foreign language, increases their self-esteem, which allows them to better perceive and master grammatical and lexical constructions. All of the above leads to the emergence of various types of communication, contributes to the construction of the correct statement, forms an adequate speech behavior.

An important factor is also the development of creative abilities, various types of memory, thinking, increasing attention, as well as learning to communicate with both classmates and teachers. The need to introduce various Internet technologies in the process of teaching a foreign language to students with disabilities is beyond doubt, however, the material and technical equipment of places of study in this social category does not always meet the requirements.

In this regard, the use of Internet technologies becomes impossible in the process of conducting the lesson itself. As part of independent work, these technologies will make learning a foreign language more lively, fascinating and interesting, because children with certain problems with movement receive basic information from the Internet.

One of the forms of telecommunications is a podcast - a type of social service that allows you to listen, view, create and distribute audio and video broadcasts on a social network. For English learners, the podcast directory is located at the following locations:

www.podomatic.com,

www.futurelearn.com,

www.BritishCouncil.com.

The use of a social podcast server in practical classes in English to develop listening skills with secondary school students diagnosed with disabilities showed quite good results.

Inclusive education is being actively introduced into modern educational system. The use of the above methods in teaching a foreign language to students with disabilities showed that this social group quickly and relatively easily masters the proposed material, they have a high motivation to learn a foreign language. However, when conducting the study, we encountered certain difficulties, in particular, teachers' lack of readiness and ability to work with students with disabilities.

Moreover, there is a problem not only professional, but also psychological readiness to work with such a group of students. With a competent solution of these problems (training courses, exchange of experience, tutor meetings, master classes, internships - remote interactive educational programs), it is possible to minimize negative manifestations of inclusion in the educational environment of students with special educational needs.

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